

1 **GADD45 activation in inflammatory bowel disease.**

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7 We used transcriptomics for discovery of novel factors over-expressed in inflammatory bowel disease. We
8 report here activation of a family of nuclear factors that function with the *Dnmt* DNA methyltransferase
9 enzymes, *Gadd45a*, *Gadd45b* and *Gadd45g*, in the whole blood of humans with Crohn's Disease. A
10 systems biologic approach which constructs synthetic transcriptional networks based on co-regulation
11 information identified IL-17 receptor beta (*IL17RB*) and the interferon gamma receptor (*IFNGR1*) as
12 relevant targets or Gadd45-associated gene products in IBD.

13 Citations

14 1. Chathuranga, W.G., Nikapitiya, C., Kim, J.H., Chathuranga, K., Weerawardhana, A., Dodantenna,
15 N., Kim, D.J., Poo, H., Jung, J.U., Lee, C.H. and Lee, J.S., 2023. Gadd45 β is critical for regulation of type I
16 interferon signaling by facilitating G3BP-mediated stress granule formation. *Cell Reports*, 42(11).

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GSE186507